

Figure S2: Comparison of species tree obtained from Astral with genomic data, concatenated maximum likelihood tree with genomic data, and mtDNA likelihood tree with only one specimen sampled per species.

Figure S3: Support for varying levels of hybridization (H_{max}) from Snaq analyses across (A) a subset of all rattlesnake species, (B) within the *C. triseriatus* group, (C) within the *C. durissus* group, and (D) within the *C. viridis* group.

Figure S4a: All Snaq networks obtained under varying values of H_{max} examined across a subset of all rattlesnake species. An H_{max} of 3 was the best supported with these data.

Figure S4b: : All Snaq networks obtained under varying values of H max examined within the *C. viridis* species group.

Figure S4c: : All Snaq networks obtained under varying values of H max examined within the *C. triseriatus* species group.

Figure S4d: : All Snaq networks obtained under varying values of H_{max} examined within the *C. durissus* species group.